

THE ROLE OF A PROFESSIONAL PSYCHOLOGIST IN PSYCHOLOGICAL ADAPTATION TO PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

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Annotation: Adaptation to professional activity is the process of a person entering a profession, expressed in its goals, content, technologies, means of implementation, order and intensity of activity, production and labor discipline, organizational rules and norms, and flexibility to other requirements. It is believed that external assistance from professional psychologists, including instructors, reduces the difficulties of adaptation and contributes to success in overcoming difficulties in ensuring adaptation to the social conditions in which a specialist's professional activity takes place. In this sense, the peculiarities of adaptation to professional activity have been analyzed.

Keywords: professional psychologist, professional activity, adaptation, biological, physiological, psychological, social, socio-psychological, professional, adaptation stages, personal adaptive potential, neuro-psychological stability, communicative characteristics, moral normativity, adaptive potential.

1. Introduction

According to psychologists, uncertainty is one of the problems of the modern world (instability of the future, rapid development of technology, axiological uncertainty, mobility, polyphony of the social environment, etc.), and uncertainty is particularly evident in the profession of a military personnel [1; 2].

The duty to recognize uncertain situations and to begin to fulfill assigned tasks in any situation requires a serviceman to be flexible in the requirements of this profession. In the military profession, the level of flexibility is important, and it is precisely the adaptation to the process of military professional activity that is characterized by a number of characteristics.

This article analyzes the psychological aspects of the adaptation process to professional activity, the role of a professional psychologist in this process, and the results of empirical research on the adaptation process.

2. Materials and methods

Various studies have been conducted on the personality's adaptation to general professional activity, and its specificity is linked to activity. K.K. Platonov, in his Brief Explanatory Dictionary of Psychological Concepts, defines activity as follows: "Activity is understood as the conscious, purposeful activity of a person and their integral socio-psychological qualities, which are dialectically interconnected, defining and characterizing the degree or extent of the subject's personal influence on the objects, processes, and phenomena of the surrounding reality." [3; p-96.].

The term "adaptation" was first used in science by G. Auberg and is widely used in the natural, technical, and social sciences. This term originates from the Latin word "*adaptatio*" and means adjustment, adaptation. Adaptation, along with philosophical categories as a general scientific concept, serves to unify the objects studied in different sciences into a unified theoretical structure [4].

Depending on a person's interaction with the environment, adaptation types are divided into: biological, physiological, psychological, social, socio-psychological, and professional. Psychological adaptation manifests itself as an adaptation of the individual to conditions and tasks at the level of mental processes. Depending on the mechanisms of development, physiology distinguishes between rapid and long-term adaptation. Rapid adaptation is innate and changes little under the influence of the environment, unlike long-term adaptation, which is a gradual adaptation of the organism to the effects of stimuli [5].

The problem of adaptation is illuminated in the works of E. Erikson, A. Maslow, G. Allport, and R. Lazarus. In this regard, E. Erikson interprets socio-psychological adaptation as a homeostatic balance between the demands of the environment and the internal stimuli of the individual. The conflict arises due to the mismatch between the individual's needs and the demands of the environment, leading to a state of anxiety [5].

Psychoanalysts (G. Hartmann) distinguish between adaptation as a process and adaptation as a result of the process. According to G. Hartmann, productivity, the ability to enjoy life, and mental balance are considered intact in a well-adapted person. In the process of adaptation, both humans and the environment actively change, resulting in a state of adaptation between them. The adaptation process is managed by the EGO [6].

V.S. Sablin believes that the speed of adaptation is the achievement of a certain degree of adaptation over a certain period of time. This parameter indicates that each person has a certain ability to adapt. Adaptation dynamics encompasses periods of time characterizing some characteristics of qualitative and quantitative changes in the content of the adaptation process. This is called adaptation stages. They are divided into 3 groups [7]:

Table 1.
Adaptation steps

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
<p>it is approximate, characterized by contradictions between the expectations of the adaptive person and the actual state of affairs, and is characterized by restraint in communication and rigidity in behavior.</p>	<p>is a real adaptation characterized by an assessment of the level of compliance with the set requirements and their application by group members.</p> <p>The individual develops a communication and action strategy aimed at establishing consistency between the requirements set, their application, and implementation among group members.</p>	<p>stabilization is characterized by the establishment of a dynamic balance in the relationship between the adaptive individual and the social environment, when the set requirements correspond to their implementation among group members. For a flexible person, this is a state of adaptation.</p>

The higher the pace of adaptation, the less time it takes for the individual to adapt to the group, and the higher their ability to adapt. A number of methods can be used to determine the level of adaptability. Among them, the "Adaptability" questionnaire by A.G. Maklakov and S.V. Chermyanin [8] is considered effective in studying participants' characteristics such as neuro-psychological stability (NPS), communicative potential (CP), and moral normativity (MN), as well as personal adaptive potential (PAP).

3. Result and discussion

According to the analysis, the results on the reliability scale showed a large number of subjects, mainly of medium and high levels. All participants scored high on the Personal Adaptation Potential (PAP) scale, indicating good adaptability to new operating conditions and emotional resilience. The results on the neuro-psychological stability (NPS) scale were positive, and there were virtually no participants with low scores among the participants. The results obtained on the scale of communicative characteristics (CC) indicate that their communicative characteristics are generally positive. Our study did not observe subjects with a low level of moral norms. The results obtained are presented in Picture 1.

Picture 1. "Adaptability" questionnaire indicators

The effectiveness of adaptation largely depends on the genetically determined characteristics of the nervous system, as well as on learning conditions, stereotypes of learned behavior, and the adequacy of a person's self-esteem. The adaptation process is very dynamic. Its success largely depends on a number of objective and subjective conditions, functional state, social experience, life attitude, and others. Every person reacts differently to the same events, and different people may react differently to a stimulus that acts the same way [8].

The relationship between the components of the participants' flexibility and psychological state is unique, which is of great importance.

Table 2.

The connection between adaptability and mental state

Adaptability	Personal Adaptation Potential (PAP)	Neuro-psychological stability (NPS)	Communicative characteristics (CC)	Moral normativity (MN)
Mental status indicators				
Moral normativity (MN)	0,072*	0,062*	0,048	0,053*
Neuroticism	0,093*	0,104**	0,067	0,007**
Spontaneous aggression	0,113**	0,097*	0,086*	0,072*
Depression	0,116**	0,115**	0,115**	0,008**
Reactive Aggression	0,013	0,009**	0,026	-0,003**
Emotional lability	0,104**	0,108**	0,086**	0,016

Comment: * $p \leq 0,05$; ** $p \leq 0,01$

According to the analysis results, it can be seen that with the increase in the participants' Personal Adaptive Potential (PAT), their moral normativeness (MN) also increases. This also affects their areas of neuroticism, involuntary aggression, depression, and ensures a decrease in emotional instability. The area of

"Neuro-psychological stability (NPS)" is also related to all the characteristics of the psychological state of the subjects, and the more balanced the nervous-psychological stability of the participants is, the more convenient it is for them to fulfill the requirements of moral norms (MN). If the opposite is true, this leads to increased nervousness, aggression, and depression based on regrets in the subjects. Unlike other aspects, "communicative characteristics (CC)" increase this feature ensures a decrease in the level of aggression and depression among participants. That is, negative elements in the mental state can be eliminated due to communicative characteristics. A clear reflection of moral norms (MN) leads to a decrease in nervousness, aggression, and depression among participants.

Based on the characteristics studied, the adaptive abilities of participants play an important role in expressing their mental state, ensuring the effectiveness of the socio-psychological adaptation process in various conditions and determining their personal adaptive potential (AP). The characteristics of personal adaptive potential can be obtained by assessing behavioral regulation, communication skills, and the level of moral norms.

4. Conclusion

In general, adaptation can vary depending on the types of professions and their specifics. "Adaptation is a method, form of activity that allows students in higher education to adapt to various situations, reducing the level of tension in students' professional activities and increasing their adaptive abilities, stimulating their activities in the educational process" [9]. Also, professional adaptation is the process of a person entering a profession and harmonizing their activities with the professional environment. Training a specialist for activities that are complex, extreme, and unconventional in nature is carried out in a unique way. It is understood that the successful entry of a specialist into professional activity is accompanied by adaptation processes.

Research has shown that the process of adaptation is not always successful. Sooner or later, adaptation disruption must occur under different conditions, and in some participants it happens very early, while in others it happens much later. This situation depends not only on the circumstances, but also on the personal characteristics of the participants, and requires preventive measures to be taken with them.

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